

Producing High-fidelity Synthetic Population Ensembles at Scale

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Abstract—Used within social simulations, synthetic population ensembles enable uncertainty quantification (UQ) methods for obtaining more robust model inference and prediction. A synthetic population ensemble is a series of plausible virtual reconstructions of an area’s population at the granularity of people and residences, generated stochastically to preserve privacy of the source population survey’s respondents. In this paper, we demonstrate the production of large synthetic population ensembles for the US via Oak Ridge National Laboratory’s UrbanPop framework to support modeling of high spatial resolution energy affordability metrics from nationwide social surveys in collaboration with the fusionACS project. Our initial task involves creating ensembles for 17 US metropolitan areas, each consisting of 41 population instances (a base realization and 40 replicates). To accomplish this task at scale, we configured an integrated system comprised of a research cloud, virtual containerization, GPU-enhanced functionality, and a dual API/CLI to interact with UrbanPop’s maturing Likeness Python ecosystem. We observe a reduction in theoretical execution time while maintaining high-fidelity approximations of residential totals by metropolitan area *and* the demographic characteristics of neighborhoods. We discuss expansion of our approach to produce synthetic population ensembles for the entire US, particularly plans to establish automated workflows for job orchestration to increase computational efficiency, as well as provide outlook for broadening applications of the ensembles.

Index Terms—synthetic population ensembles, social simulation, human dynamics, workflow containerization, cluster computing, GPU-enabled computing

I. INTRODUCTION

Social simulations in human dynamics research often apply an individual-level representation of population to understand the collective outcomes of complex social processes, including transportation and energy use [1], disease transmission [2], and disaster response [3]. A common source of individual-level data is *synthetic populations*, which virtually reconstruct an area’s population across localities (e.g., neighborhoods) on a

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selection of population features (e.g., demographic, economic, housing, and mobility characteristics) [4]. Population synthesis involves statistically matching official population statistics for small census areas (i.e., <10k people) using anonymized population surveys available at a coarser spatial resolution [5]. This is achieved through estimation of *small-area population weights*, which consist of representative counts of $\{1..n\}$ entities across $\{1..m\}$ localities in an area of interest (AOI). This approach provides a mechanism for stochastic generation of individual/household entities from the survey and avoids identification of an area’s actual residents.

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) for social simulations uses a model ensemble based on multiple representations of an area’s population to obtain more robust inference on social processes [6]. To support UQ, *synthetic population ensembles* are generated by leveraging variability from the population survey’s sampling design or the small-area weights estimation procedure. In this paper, we detail extending the capabilities of Oak Ridge National Laboratory’s (ORNL) UrbanPop framework [7] to produce synthetic population ensembles across the United States (US), supporting spatial refinement of energy affordability indicators from social surveys by the fusionACS project. UrbanPop uses the US Census Bureau’s American Community Survey (ACS) to produce high-fidelity synthetic population ensembles. The UrbanPop ensembles in turn provide small-area weights and UQ for the fusionACS model, which simulates household responses to a social survey by conflating demographic, economic, and housing variables with those assigned to synthetic residences via the ACS [8].

In the following sections, we describe the process of establishing compute infrastructure on the ORNL Research Cloud (ORC) to support estimation of UrbanPop ensembles at scale for the United States, including containerization of the Likeness Python ecosystem and the development of tooling for efficiently handling preprocessing, model execution, and data generation tasks. We explain these tasks in the context of an initial objective to produce UrbanPop ensembles for 17 US metropolitan areas consisting of 41 realizations each, providing validation and benchmarks for the procedure, as well as the outlook for its extension to the full US.

II. SYNTHETIC POPULATION MODELING CAPABILITIES

A. *UrbanPop*

UrbanPop produces high-fidelity synthetic populations for the United States at the annual cadence of ACS releases [9]. Unlike the Decennial (10-year) Census, which represents a complete count of the US population, the ACS is a 5% sample that is extrapolated to the full population [10]. In addition to more rapid releases, the ACS contains considerably more detail on demographic, economic, mobility, and housing characteristics than the Decennial Census. While many other synthetic population frameworks for the US rely upon the ACS, UrbanPop is distinguished by the large volume of variables it can accommodate [7]. In addition to providing rich attribution of the resulting synthetic population, this means that the small-area weights used to synthesize people and residences are informed by potentially hundreds of constraints drawn from different subjects across the ACS, providing a more robust sampling basis for population synthesis than is available in similar models.

B. *Likeness*

UrbanPop scales capabilities from the maturing Likeness Python ecosystem, including processing large swaths of ACS data, performing population synthesis, and activity modeling [11], [12]. Likeness operates on the ACS 5-Year Estimates, providing small-area weights natively for block groups (600-3,000 people) within a Public-Use Microdata Area (PUMA – 100,000 or more people) based on responses from the ACS Public-Use Microdata Sample (PUMS). The primary goal of the population synthesis procedure is to reconstruct constraints (population features) of interest at the block group level using the small-area weights to match the uncertainty (e.g., 90% Margins of Error) on the published estimates of those variables from the ACS Summary File (SF). This process initializes with sample weights from the PUMS, which estimate the representativeness of each person/household record within its PUMA ($1..n \times 1$). Alternative realizations of the PUMS sample weights are obtainable from the PUMS replicate weights. Replicate weights represent statistical variation in the estimated occurrences of residential entities within the PUMS and support up to 81 rounds of small-area weights estimation per PUMA.

At a high level, population synthesis within Likeness requires integrating layers from multiple ACS datasets, including the PUMS, SF (estimates and standard errors), and geographic relationship files into a symbolic representation of a PUMA. The *livelike* package provides these capabilities through utilities for fetching and processing ACS data through the Census ACS SF and Microdata APIs, as well as translating PUMS variables to ACS SF variables to build constraints that link the individual and geographic scales. These utilities ensure that all PUMAs within an AOI are constructed in a consistent and reproducible way. For the sake of scalability (e.g., avoiding connection timeouts when fetching ACS data for multiple PUMAs simultaneously), we mimic the Census

API functionality internally using *sqlalchemy* [13] to access ACS data snapshots hosted on PostgreSQL databases [14]. This is accomplished through a currently closed-source package within the Likeness ecosystem (*pronto-gatto*).

PUMA instances constructed with *livelike* provide all the necessary ingredients to estimate small-area weights for block groups within a PUMA. Likeness handles weights estimation by passing the PUMA inputs to the Penalized Maximum-Entropy Dasymetric Modeling (P-MEDM) solver. Specifically, *livelike* depends upon *pymedm*, a Python-native implementation of P-MEDM¹ that offers GPU acceleration for rapid solve time via *jax* [15] and *jaxopt* [16].

The efficient P-MEDM solve time from *pymedm* on GPU-enabled systems allows problems for multiple PUMA replicates to be designed and solved sequentially to produce a synthetic population ensemble. In addition to the base sample weights, the PUMS also contains 80 person/household weights accounting for sampling variation. The base weights are used to produce an initial synthetic population, with $\{1..r\}$ replicate weights substituted in to build the synthetic population ensemble.

C. *UrbanPop* and *fusionACS*

UrbanPop enables *fusionACS* to produce high-resolution estimates of well-being indicators from nationwide social surveys that cover subjects like health, energy, and transportation. The *fusionACS* methodology applies a gradient boosting approach to predict responses to questions from these “donor” social surveys onto PUMS residential records via common demographic, economic, and housing characteristics [8]. Whereas *fusionACS* was previously limited to PUMA resolution, UrbanPop now enables simulation of these responses with synthetic population ensembles, supporting *fusionACS* variable estimates at high spatial resolution (block groups). This is accomplished through the *fusionACS* point estimation and UQ procedures by substituting small-area weights from synthetic population ensembles in place of the base PUMS replicate weights. The enhanced output supplies a comprehensive set of social indicators across localities, which in the context of our focus on energy affordability, is useful for tasks like exploring the intersection between energy and localized outcomes of severe weather events that disrupt power grids, such as heat waves [17] and winter storms [18].

III. TASK DESCRIPTION

The initial objective of the UrbanPop and *fusionACS* collaboration involves downscaling indicators from the 2020 Residential Energy Consumption Survey (RECS)² to census tract resolution (800-1,200 people)³ using a synthetic population ensembles consisting of a baseline population and 40 replicates

¹Original implementation authored in C++ with an R wrapper, see: <https://bitbucket.org/nnagle/pmedmrcpp/src/master>

²<https://www.eia.gov/consumption/residential/>

³UrbanPop models synthetic populations at the more granular block group level to support the highest spatial resolution available from the ACS. Since block groups nest within tracts, *fusionACS* aggregates them to tract level simply by summing block group weights within each tract.

across 17 Core-based Metropolitan Statistical (CBSAs) in the United States. Each CBSA forms a distinct AOI, listed in Table I and shown in Fig. 1. Table I provides a “Label” and “Shorthand” for each CBSA that can be used as a reference to link the information in all following Tables and Figures in this manuscript, along with a full official name and CBSA Federal Information Processing Standards (FIPS) code. These CBSAs were selected for their demographic profiles, populations, and varied geographies, as seen in Fig. 1. As with the population distribution in the US as a whole, the selected CBSAs are concentrated in the eastern half of the continental US with the largest cluster in the “BosWash” Megalopolis, stretching in the north from Boston to Washington, D.C. in the south. This megaregion contains both the most and least populated model AOIs in our study set: New York and Vineland, respectively, and is highlighted in the Fig. 1 inset (with the exception of Boston). The inset also clearly demonstrates both possible areal configurations for CBSA/PUMA relationships where the aggregate PUMA bounds can be 1) equal to the bounds of a CBSA – as in the case of Philadelphia – or 2) larger than the bounds of a CBSA – as in the case of Baltimore. CBSAs can never be larger than the aggregate PUMAs since PUMAs are comprised of whole counties and/or census tracts.

TABLE I
THE 17 CORE-BASED STATISTICAL AREAS (CBSAS) SELECTED FOR SYNTHETIC POPULATION GENERATION (VISUALIZED IN FIG. 1).

Label	FIPS	Name	Shorthand
0	12060	Atlanta-Sandy Springs-Alpharetta	atlanta
1	12580	Baltimore-Columbia-Towson	baltimore
2	14460	Boston-Cambridge-Newton	boston
3	16980	Chicago-Napier-Elgin	chicago
4	19100	Dallas-Plano-Irving	dallas
5	47900	Washington-Arlington-Alexandria	dc
6	19820	Detroit-Warren-Dearborn	detroit
7	31080	Los Angeles-Long Beach-Anaheim	la
8	35380	New Orleans-Metarie	nola
9	35620	New York-Newark-Jersey City	nyc
10	37980	Philadelphia-Camden-Wilmington	phila
11	41700	San Antonio-New Braunfels	sanant
12	41860	San Francisco-Oakland-Berkeley	sanfran
13	42660	Seattle-Bellevue-Kent	seattle
14	41620	Salt Lake City	slc
15	41180	St. Louis	stlouis
16	47220	Vineland-Bridgeton	vineland

We applied the Likeness Python stack to formulate and solve a series of P-MEDM problems for the PUMAs covering each CBSA’s boundaries, providing high spatial resolution estimates of PUMS residences at the block group level. Here we define “residences” as housing units (including vacant housing units) and group quarters (e.g., college dormitories, nursing homes, prisons). Each residence contains a subset of the PUMA population (e.g., household members). Regarding the weighting schema, housing units are weighted by PUMS household weights and group quarters are weighted by PUMS person weights. We take this approach because group quarters are special cases in which each person is considered to independently occupy a residential unit.

For all CBSAs, 41 synthetic populations were generated for each comprising PUMA by solving the representative P-MEDM instance – 1 base realization (denoted as 0) and 40 replicate realizations (1 – 40). Each P-MEDM problem (29,233 in total) was solved on 254 constraining variables from the ACS SF, encompassing demographic, social, economic, worker/student, mobility, housing, and technical (sampling universe) characteristics. The constraining variable themes, subjects, and descriptions are shown in Table II.

Our use of a base realization and 40 replicates is guided by fusionACS, whose selection balances robust statistical representation with reduced compute time and file storage requirements [8]. In our case, while 80 replicates are provided by the ACS, this would double both the time for computation and the file storage needs, which is discussed further in Section V-A.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Architecture

Solving a single P-MEDM instance for a PUMA is a relatively trivial task when compared to other numerical optimization methods [19]⁴. For example, one PUMA-based P-MEDM problem can be solved on a CPU processor in approximately 1.5 minutes (though times vary greatly with both machine specifications and the unique properties of individual models). In order to accomplish the generation of synthetic populations for 41 PUMA instances across all model AOIs, we needed to configure a new infrastructure to ingest our code base that was both virtualized and GPU-enabled. Fig. 2 illustrates the current system layout that we built for this project to accommodate the scaled needs, as is described next.

We begin with the ORC cluster, a virtual machine infrastructure hosted on ORNL servers. This cluster is composed of both CPU-only and GPU-enabled machines that is the basis on which our application runs. The ORC cluster communicates with two types of primary external resources:

- *Code Repositories* – The project’s codebase is split between two sets of repositories. Public-facing components are hosted on GitHub, while proprietary modules are managed via ORNL’s internal GitLab instance (discussed later in Section IV-B). This dually-hosted codebase setup enables collaborative development while maintaining access control for components that have yet to be approved for public dissemination.
- *Container Registries* – The project utilizes two container registries: Harbor⁵ and DockerHub. An internal Harbor instance serves as our Docker image registry. Storing images in Harbor allows us to manage versioning and access control within a secure, centralized registry. DockerHub provides the base and shared images used across many parts of the system. It acts as a global registry for standardized containers.

⁴See also Section 3.2 of [7] and Eq. 1 in [11].

⁵<https://goharbor.io/>

17 Selected CBSAs and Model AOIs - 2019

Fig. 1. The 17 CBSAs found in Table I and modeled AOIs (collections of PUMAs) from 2019. The inset demonstrates that the bounds of a CBSA can be as large (e.g., in Philadelphia) or smaller (e.g., in Baltimore) than the modeled AOI, but never larger.

Docker is used within ORC to deploy images retrieved from Harbor where containerization allows for modular, reproducible environments and isolates dependencies across applications. Once deployed, containers run on the matched node types: CPU-based images on the CPU node and GPU-enabled applications on GPU nodes.

We utilize multiple systems with varying configurations. Our CPU-only system runs Ubuntu 22.04 and is equipped with an AMD EPYC 7702 64-Core Processor and 62GB of memory with no swap space configured. Our GPU-enabled systems also run Ubuntu 22.04 and are equipped with an AMD EPYC 9754 128-Core Processor, 62GB of memory, and no swap space configured. Each GPU virtual machine instance is allocated one NVIDIA (CUDA 12.6) L40S GPU with 46GB of VRAM.

The primary application, `build_ensembles` generates the final result of the pipeline: Synthetic Population Weights Ensembles. These results are used in downstream analyses and modeling workflows.

B. Python Software Stack and Dependencies

As discussed in Section I, the Likeness ecosystem is written primarily in Python, and is pinned to Python=3.11|3.12 due to stipulations in upstream dependencies whose functionalities

are not required in the study. The main upstream dependencies utilized from the scientific Python stack are shown in Table III. The Likeness stack relies heavily on array and tabular operations, which are performed via `numpy` [20], `pandas` [21], [22], and `dask` [23], [24]; ACS data retrieval from PostgreSQL databases is performed via `sqlalchemy` [13]; and the JAX ecosystem is utilized for `jax` [15] and `jaxopt` [16] numerical optimization routines.

We utilize two platforms for hosting code repositories in the Likeness ecosystem – GitHub for our external, open-source code base, and ORNL’s internal GitLab instance for repositories that have not yet been cleared for release. The ecosystem packages that are used within this study are shown in Table IV with specifications on where they are hosted, their open-source status, and the versions used to generate synthetic populations for this project. The recently open-sourced portion of the Likeness ecosystem (currently available via GitHub⁶) contains 2 package repositories described previously in Section II-B, `livelike` and `pymedm`, along with `likeness-vitals` and 2 other packages that are not used in this study. The 2 primary internal packages that are used are `pronto-gatto` (mentioned above in Section I) and `build_ensembles`,

⁶<https://github.com/likeness-pop>

TABLE II
THEMES, SUBJECTS, AND DESCRIPTIONS FOR 254 ACS SF VARIABLES USED TO CONSTRAIN P-MEDM PROBLEMS IN THIS STUDY.

Theme	Subject Name	Description
Universe	population	Total population
	group_quarters_pop	Group quarters population
	housing_units	Housing units count
	occhu	Occupied housing units
	civ_noninst_pop	Civilian non-institutionalized population
Worker	emp_stat	Employment status
Student	sexnaics	Sex by NAICS (North American Industry Classification System) industry – https://www.census.gov/naics/ .
Mobility	grade	School grade level
	commute	Commuter time to work
Demographic	travel	Means of travel to work
	sex_age	Sex by age
	hhtype	Household type
Social	hhtype_hhsize	Household type by household size
	race	Race
	hsplat	Hispanic/Latino origin
Economic	edu_attainment	Educational attainment for population 25+ by sex by age
	hhinc	Household income, adjusted for inflation
Housing	rooms	Total rooms in dwelling
	units	Units in structure
	year_built	Year of dwelling construction
	hhf	House heating fuel
	rentcost	Monthly gross rent as % of household income in the last 12 months by tenure
	owncost	Monthly homeowner housing costs as % of household income in the last 12 months by mortgage status

TABLE III
MAJOR UPSTREAM DEPENDENCIES IN THE SCIENTIFIC PYTHON STACK.

Package Name	Version
python	3.12.9
dask	2025.3.0
jax	0.4.31
jaxopt	0.8.3
numpy	2.2.4
pandas	2.2.3
sqlalchemy	2.0.40

- *preprocessing* – generating and storing PUMA objects
- *solving* – solving P-MEDM representations of individual PUMA realizations
- *assembling* – combining individual PUMA-realization results into aggregate files
- *validating* – verifying the accuracy and reliability of results

which was developed specifically for this project.

Having discussed the means by which we implement our workflow, we now turn to its functionality (`build_ensembles`), inspecting and validating its resultant synthetic population weights ensembles, and discussing its limitations and planned enhancements.

TABLE IV
PACKAGES WITHIN THE LIKENESS ECOSYSTEM USED FOR THIS STUDY, BOTH OPEN-SOURCED AND CURRENTLY CLOSED-SOURCED.

Package Name	Hosted On	Open	Version
likeness-vitals	GitHub	✓	1.4.4
livelike	GitHub	✓	1.4.8
pymedm	GitHub	✓	2.2.4
pronto-gatto	GitLab	✗	0.2.9
build_ensembles	GitLab	✗	0.0.5

C. Workflow

The `build_ensembles` workflow can be broken down into 4 stages:

The functionality comprising these stages can be accessed via both an application programming interface (API) and a command line interface (CLI). The API is hierarchical, consisting of publicly-exposed top-level functions to perform the 4 stages described above (*preprocessing*, *solving*, *assembling*, and *validating*), along with utilities for fetching “recipes” (job parameters including administrative unit codes, constraining variables, ACS vintage, etc.) and various other diagnostic tasks. A CLI was developed to assist in the launching of jobs via Docker containers, which collates API functionality and default argument values specifically for ease of use while running programs on ORC (i.e., default database credentials and data read/write locations).

As mentioned above, we are emphasizing the *solving* stage of our workflow and the associated functionality available within `build_ensembles`. Below are 2 examples of solving a single PUMA realization from the API and the CLI (Listing 1 and Listing 2, respectively) – the base realization (0) of PUMA 3402400 within the Vineland-Bridgeton, New Jersey CBSA. Both Listing 1 and Listing 2 accomplish the exact same task and generate identical output.

Fig. 2. System architecture and workflow for the implementation of the UrbanPop framework with the Likeness ecosystem for this project.

```

1 from build_ensembles.solve_pmedm import solve_pmedm
2 from build_ensembles.utils import read_recipe
3
4 # Solve the P-MEDM instance for
5 # the base realization of PUMA 3402400 in the Vineland, NJ CBSA
6 solve_pmedm(
7     "metro",
8     read_recipe("vineland"),
9     "3402400",
10    0,
11 )

```

Listing 1. build_ensembles API: solving a P-MEDM instance.

```

1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 # Solve the P-MEDM instance for
4 # the base realization of PUMA 3402400 in the Vineland, NJ CBSA
5 up_solve_pmedm_cli \
6     --aoi_type metro \
7     --single-recipe vineland \
8     --solve_by_puma 3402400 \
9     --solve_by_realization 0

```

Listing 2. build_ensembles CLI: solving a P-MEDM instance.

V. RESULTS

A. Execution Timing

The clear bottleneck in our workflow introduced in Section IV-A is not a tractable solve time for individual P-MEDM instances, it is the aggregate solve time for all P-MEDM

instances. Therefore, here we will be focusing on timings from the *solving* stage introduced in Section IV-C by reporting granular and aggregate duration of execution, which are shown in Table V.

TABLE V
PREDICTED AND OBSERVED EXECUTION TIMES (SECONDS) FOR SOLVING # P-MEDM INSTANCES FOR EACH CBSA.

	count P-MEDM #	seconds		
		Predicted Σ	Observed Σ	μ
atlanta	1 845	36 900	19 561.00	10.60
baltimore	902	18 040	13 920.42	15.43
boston	1 599	31 980	23 939.93	14.97
chicago	2 706	54 120	45 512.01	16.82
dallas	2 337	46 740	25 359.03	10.85
dc	1 927	38 540	27 304.54	14.17
detroit	1 230	24 600	28 538.87	23.20
la	3 567	71 340	58 333.36	16.35
nola	410	8 200	8 949.36	21.83
nyc	5 986	119 720	93 449.02	15.61
phila	1 804	36 080	28 128.58	15.59
sanant	861	17 220	9 077.32	10.54
sanfran	1 394	27 880	19 333.37	13.87
seattle	1 189	23 780	15 321.40	12.89
slc	410	8 200	3 933.77	9.59
stlouis	984	19 680	17 034.52	17.31
vineland	82	1 640	923.75	11.27
	Σ 29 233	Σ 584 660	Σ 438 620.23	μ 14.76

For each CBSA, Table V details the number of solved P-MEDM instances (P-MEDM #), the expected aggregate solve time (Predicted \sum), and the observed aggregate and mean solve times (Observed \sum and Observed μ) where solve times are reported in seconds. The expected aggregate solve times are based on conservative estimate of preliminary solve time of ≈ 20 seconds per P-MEDM⁷ when executed on a processor with GPU-enhanced capabilities. This equates to a predicted aggregate theoretical solve time for 29,233 P-MEDM instances (41 instances per PUMA per CBSA) of 2.7067 days (584,660 seconds). The aggregate theoretical solve time can be compared to our obtained observed aggregate solve time of 2.031 days (438,620.23 seconds). While we may have expected to see approximately half that due to the “manually parallel” 2-GPU paradigm we needed to employ – running at most 2 CBSAs at a time – the true clocktime was in fact closer to 3 full days. This can be attributed to the manual nature of CBSA-based job launching where downtime (i.e., a CBSA finished during the night) played a non-trivial role in increasing the overall start-to-finish duration while not affecting actual solve time.

We observed a grand mean solve time of 14.759 seconds per P-MEDM across all PUMA realizations in all 17 CBSAs, with minimum mean solve time per PUMA of 9.59 seconds in Salt Lake City and a maximum mean solve time per PUMA of 23.2 seconds in Detroit. The variation in mean solve times across CBSAs can be attributed to the unique properties of each model (i.e., like cities themselves, no 2 PUMAs are exactly alike – especially from a demographic standpoint) which leads to some models being more difficult to solve than others.

B. Verification & Validation

In order to ensure the accuracy of the P-MEDM results (synthetic population weights), we perform 2 verification and validation tasks: the calculation and comparison of 1) observed total residences to synthetic total residences; and 2) the proportion of P-MEDM constraining variables conforming to published 90% Margins of Error (MOE Fit Rate) in the ACS SF by block group and PUMA based on the estimated small-area weights (“MOE Fit Rates”).

To validate counts of total residences, we employ the mean absolute error (MAE) of the observed (ACS SF) total residence counts for each CBSA as compared to the base realization and 40 replicate synthetic populations. The results, shown in Table VI, illustrate that we are invariably reproducing counts that faithfully match the empirically observed counts with a grand MAE of 0.00066. This MAE is well below 1% for generating a synthetic population of 40,799,248 residences in 17 CBSAs, which represents $\approx 28.03\%$ of the official ACS estimate of total residences in the US in 2019 (145,519,985).

For the MOE Fit Rates task, we perform a direct comparison of the published 90% rates per administrative census unit to the observed rates across each CBSA. Table VII shows that

⁷We observed a preliminary observed solve time of ≈ 15 seconds for most PUMAs, then buffered that for potentially longer solve times.

TABLE VI
MEAN OF ABSOLUTE ERROR (MAE) OF SYNTHETIC TOTAL RESIDENCES CONFORMITY TO OFFICIAL ACS TOTALS OVER 41 REALIZATIONS.

	Known Total	$MAE_{i=0}^{n=40}$
atlanta	2663993	0.00026
baltimore	1294043	0.00058
boston	2299776	0.00021
chicago	4031225	0.00033
dallas	2895592	0.00024
dc	2725516	0.00047
detroit	1996891	0.00041
la	4866658	0.00023
nola	580217	0.00059
nyc	8159594	0.00024
phila	2663798	0.00057
sanant	1038256	0.00056
sanfran	1889830	0.00033
seattle	1660732	0.00047
slc	452013	0.00053
stlouis	1482681	0.00040
vineland	98433	0.00478
\sum	40799248	μ
		0.00066

we are reproducing mean MOE Fit Rates exceeding 99.85% in every CBSA across the 41 realizations of synthetic population at both the block group- and PUMA-levels, with very low standard deviations: <0.005 at the block group-level and <0.001 at the PUMA-level. Taken as a whole, these represent a grand mean and standard deviation of: $\mu = 0.9992, \sigma = 0.0005$.

TABLE VII
CONSTRAINING VARIABLE MARGIN OF ERROR FIT RATES AT THE BLOCK GROUP- AND PUMA-LEVEL.

	MOE			
	block group		PUMA	
	μ	σ	μ	σ
atlanta	0.9993	0.0021	0.9993	0.0003
baltimore	0.9991	0.0028	0.9991	0.0005
boston	0.9995	0.0016	0.9995	0.0002
chicago	0.9992	0.0033	0.9991	0.0009
dallas	0.9993	0.0020	0.9993	0.0004
dc	0.9991	0.0028	0.9992	0.0005
detroit	0.9994	0.0021	0.9994	0.0004
la	0.9995	0.0018	0.9995	0.0002
nola	0.9994	0.0024	0.9993	0.0004
nyc	0.9987	0.0037	0.9988	0.0009
phila	0.9992	0.0025	0.9992	0.0006
sanant	0.9991	0.0030	0.9990	0.0006
sanfran	0.9992	0.0023	0.9992	0.0005
seattle	0.9994	0.0020	0.9993	0.0003
slc	0.9994	0.0030	0.9994	0.0007
stlouis	0.9987	0.0030	0.9987	0.0006
vineland	0.9990	0.0032	0.9990	0.0005
μ	0.9992	0.0026	0.9992	0.0005

VI. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE WORK

The 17 CBSAs selected by fusionACS were used for preliminary model calibration, estimation, and visualization

of energy affordability indicators from RECS⁸. A large proportion of United States total residences ($\approx 71.97\%$) remain unaccounted for by this exercise, many of which occur within rural regions of the country. Differences in energy affordability between urban and rural areas remain of key interest for future collaborations with fusionACS. To support these future efforts, the next major milestone is to produce synthetic population ensembles covering the entirety of the US with base realizations and 40 replicates. We will accomplish this by transitioning from a “metro area”-based AOI approach to one considering Census Divisions⁹ as AOIs, allowing us to fully canvass the US while keeping our workflow decentralized. We expect this task to significantly increase execution time beyond what our current “manual parallelization” schema (Section V-A) can handle, leading to the need for proper job orchestration.

To advance our current methods, we look to recent and related ORNL efforts focused on large-scale population modeling and human mobility simulation such as HumoNet [25] and DICER [26] that have implemented cloud-based job orchestration workflows to produce, model, and analyze massive datasets from complex routines in feasible execution time. The 2 challenges described below each encapsulate a limitation and potential opportunity for future enhancement that is displayed in Fig. 3.

A. Hardware Availability & Parallelization

1) *Challenge*: Currently, we only have access to 1 CPU-based node and 2 GPU-enabled nodes. As reported in Section IV-C our `build_ensembles` code has 4 main stages, 3 of which can be executed in parallel to reduce processing time. While we are running these stages in parallel, it is a “manual parallel” schema as described previously. That is, our current workflow is not performed in a truly distributed manner and it is not fully automated.

2) *Opportunity*: Employing a workflow automation tool will be the cornerstone to tackling this challenge. With a tool such as `prefect`¹⁰, we will be able to spin up server and worker nodes that can distribute the workload of `build_ensembles` to multiple machines. Task distribution and code execution on certain machines based on resource availability can be handled by `prefect`, along with pausing execution until resources are free. This job launching orchestration will be helpful at all stages in our workflow, but will be critical at the solving stage for the next step of full coverage of PUMAs across the US. In 2019 there were a total of 2,351 PUMAs while our current modeling AOIs only contained a total of 713. When accounting for the number of P-MEDM realizations to solve – 1 base and 40 replicates per PUMA – the solution set balloons from 29,233 to 96,391 instances and would take roughly 16.5 days under our current schema.

⁸Preliminary results available at: https://socio-spatial-climate.shinyapps.io/FusionACS_dev/

⁹https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/economic-census/guidance-geographies/levels.html#par_textimage_34

¹⁰<https://www.prefect.io/>

B. Workflow Automation

1) *Challenge*: We have no dedicated CI/CD pipeline in place to automate our image builds and deploy or execute any of the `build_ensembles` codebase. We currently must manually build our images on individual ORC nodes and then synchronize them across our mini-cluster before code execution can begin. This is time consuming, cumbersome, and prone to human error. Moreover, it cuts into time that could be better spent in the development process on tasking such as rough edge refactoring and incorporating planned enhancements.

2) *Opportunity*: Developing a CI/CD pipeline that runs when certain criteria are met (e.g., pushing commits, opening GitLab Merge Requests, creating tags, and merging into protected branches) is critical for addressing this challenge. While not definitive, such a pipeline should include at least the following stages in order:

- [1] building `build_ensembles` images;
- [2] pushing the images to ORNL’s container registry;
- [3] building custom packages/libraries (if necessary);
- [4] running our testing suite with the new images; and
- [5] deploying to `prefect` for the remaining workflow.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a method for generating large synthetic population ensembles at scale for the United States, integrating longstanding synthetic population modeling capabilities (UrbanPop), a maturing Python software ecosystem (Likeness), and computational infrastructure encompassing containerization and GPU-enhanced processing. These capabilities support UQ for more robust inference and prediction from social simulations, in this case to support the fusion of energy affordability indicators to the ACS at high spatial resolution based on residential responses to the 2020 RECS. Applying our augmented infrastructure to support this task, we demonstrated the production of synthetic population ensembles for 17 US CBSAs in tractable execution time based on publicly-available US Census data. These ensembles are strongly representative of local population demographics by both faithfully recreating residence totals and reproducing demographic characteristics that closely match ACS margins of error when aggregated to PUMAs and block groups.

Beyond the fusionACS collaboration, the UrbanPop ensembles can be applied to support UQ and data generation tasks in a variety of active research areas, including agent-based models of disease transmission dynamics [27], analysis of spatial accessibility to essential services [12], building occupancy estimation [28], and demographic estimation to extend high-resolution gridded population models [29].

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Fig. 3. Potential next steps in workflow automation with prefect.

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